

REGIONAL HEAD STRATEGY TO BUILD POLITICAL SUPPORT WITH DPRD IN CONDITIONS OF DIVIDED GOVERNMENT IN MAROS REGENCY

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Abstract

This study aims to examine and analyze the strategy of regional heads to build political support with the DPRD in conditions of divided government in Maros Regency. The type of research used is qualitative research. The location of this research is in Maros Regency with loci at the Regent Office and the Maros Regency DPRD. While the type of data used is primary data and secondary data. Data collection techniques used are interviews, literature reviews, documents/archives, and documentation. The data analysis technique used is qualitative analysis. The results showed that the strategy of regional heads to build political support with the DPRD in conditions of divided government in Maros Regency was carried out several things, namely Coordination, Negotiation and Collaboration, Building Networking. The Three strategies are running well and are supported by legislators in carrying out the vision and mission of the Regent and Vice Regent of Maros Regency.

Keywords: Divided Government; Maros Regency; House of representative.

INTRODUCTION

The implementation of direct election of Regional Heads and Deputy Regional Heads is an important part of the decentralization process and will provide a very strategic role to Regional Heads and Deputy Regional Heads in the context of developing democratic life, justice, equality, community welfare, maintaining harmonious relations with the Government Central and among other Regional Governments to maintain the integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia [1].

In general, Decentralization has three objectives, namely: first; Political Decentralization; with the aim of building local level political infrastructure and suprastructure to become more democratic; second, administrative decentralization: aims to create a local government bureaucracy that is able to maximize the values of effectiveness, efficiency, equity/equality, third, economic decentralization with the hope of improving the welfare of society as a whole so that it becomes better than the previous situation[2].

Regional Government is the implementation of Regional Government functions carried out by regional government institutions, namely the Regional Government (Governor/Regent/Mayor) and the Regional People's Representative Council (Provincial/Regency/City DPRD). The Regional Head is the Head of the Regional Government who is democratically elected, that is, elected directly by the people in pairs with the Deputy Regional Head whose nomination is through a political party or/or individual [3].

The results of the 2020 Maros Regency Regent and Deputy Regent election process, Candidate Pair for Regent and Deputy Regent Number 2 (two), H.A. S Chaidir Syam, S.IP., M.H and Hj. Suhartina Bohari, S.E with 82,770 (eighty two thousand seven

hundred and seventy) votes defeated Candidate Pair for Regent and Deputy Regent Number 1 (One), Andi Tajerimin Nur, S.E., M. Si and H. Havid S Fasha, S.H. with a total of 48,308 (forty eight thousand three hundred and eight) votes and Candidate Pair for Regent and Deputy Regent Serial Number 3 (three), Drs. H. Andi Harmil Mattotorang, M.M and H. Andi Ilham Nadjamuddin, S.STP., M.Si with a total of 64,512 (sixty four thousand five hundred and twelve) votes.

So based on the provisions of Article 54 paragraph (1) of the Republic of Indonesia General Election Commission Regulation Number 19 of 2020 concerning Amendments to the Republic of Indonesia General Election Commission Regulation Number 9 of 2018 concerning Recapitulation of Vote Count Results and Determination of Election Results for Governor and Deputy Governor, Regent and Deputy Regent , and/or Mayor and Deputy Mayor and Maros Regency General Election Commission Decree No. 457/PL.02.6-Kpt/7309/KPU-Kab/XII/2020 concerning Determination of the Recapitulation of Vote Count Results and Results of the 2020 Maros Regent and Deputy Regent Election, the Maros Regency General Election Commission determined H.A. S Chaidir Syam, S.IP., M.H and Hj. Suhartina Bohari, S.E as the Elected Candidate Pair for Regent and Deputy Regent for the period 2020 to 2024 in the 2020 Maros Regent and Deputy Regent Election, which was subsequently ratified by the Minister of Home Affairs on behalf of the President with a Decree of the Minister of Home Affairs who was subsequently inaugurated by the Governor of South Sulawesi on February 26, 2021.

Based on the results of the 2019 Legislative General Election, members of the Maros Regency DPRD consist of the GOLKAR Party with 7 seats (20.00%); PAN 6 seats (17.14%); Nasdem 5 seats (14.12%); PKB and Hanura 4 seats (11.43%); Gerindra 3 seats (8.57%); PKS and PPP 2 seats (5.71%); and Democrats and PBB 1 seat (2.86%).

With the election of the pair H.A. S Chaidir Syam, S.IP., M.H and Hj. Suhartina Bohari, S.E as Regent and Deputy Regent of Maros Regency supported by the National Mandate Party and 3 (three) other parties namely the Crescent Star Party (PBB), United Development Party (PPP) and People's Conscience Party (HANURA) shows that executive power held by 4 (four) parties. Meanwhile, the Maros Regency DPRD is controlled by the GOLKAR Party, Nasdem Party, PKB, GERINDRA Party, PKS and the Democratic Party.

If calculated as a percentage, the National Mandate Party, Crescent Star Party, United Development Party and People's Conscience Party only have 13 seats in the Maros Regency DPRD or 36.88% of the total 35 seats. This shows that the quantity of political legitimacy and political support in parliament that regional heads have is low. This condition shows the existence of a divided government pattern or divided government.

In fact, as stated in Law Number 23 of 2014, regional government is the administration of government by the Regional Head and DPRD according to the principles of autonomy and assistance duties. This means that the Regional Head and DPRD must complement each other, coordinate, synchronize and be partners in the regional autonomy process, if they cannot synchronize then the government will not be able to run effectively, moreover it is impossible for the Regional Head to be able to carry out his vision, mission and work program within a period of five year.

RESEARCH METHODS

This writing uses a descriptive method. The types of data used are primary data and secondary data. The data collection techniques used were interviews, literature reviews, documents/archives, and documentation. The data analysis technique used is qualitative analysis. Qualitative data analysis in this study was carried out by referring to interactive models of data collection or data collection with data analysis according to Huberman and Miles in Bungin 2003 [4]. The results of data collection are then reduced by sorting the data into certain concept units, certain categories or definite themes. Furthermore, the presentation of data can be done in various forms such as sketches, synopsis, matrices or other forms. This is important to do to facilitate drawing conclusions. This activity may be carried out repeatedly depending on the number of processes and complexity of the problem, until obtaining valid and objective data.

RESULTS

That the Regional Head in carrying out an autonomous government is reflected in the regional expenditure budget policy; where government, development and social policies as outlined in the APBD, Regional Regulations must first obtain approval from the DPRD. Therefore, any policy that will be implemented by the Regional Head in order to realize his vision, mission and work program during the campaign must obtain DPRD approval as regulated in Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government.

In communicating regional government policies which are reflected through the preparation, discussion and approval of Regional Regulation Plans, RAPBD, Approval of Agreements with Inter-Regional or other parties, Regional Heads form Teams with procedures or mechanisms as regulated in Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 80 of 2015 concerning Formation Regional Legal Products, while the mechanisms or procedures for discussion and approval in the DPRD are regulated by the DPRD Rules and Regulations (Maros Regency).

There are regional legal products which are regulatory in nature, including regional regulations, regional head regulations, joint regulations with Regional Heads, and regional legal products which are stipulations, namely decisions of the Regional Head and instructions of the Regional Head. In preparing the draft regulations, a team is formed between regional apparatus units or officials appointed by the Regional Head and the Legal Bureau/Section as secretaries to carry out discussions on the principles regarding the objects being regulated, the scope and direction of the regulations which are then consulted with the Regional Secretary to obtain direction and report to Regional Head to obtain approval for draft regional regulations, which are then proposed by the Regent with an introductory note to the DPRD for discussion.

Regarding a draft regional regulation or draft regional budget and expenditure after being received by the DPRD leadership from the Regent, the DPRD Leadership submits it to the DPRD Deliberation Committee to obtain a discussion time schedule. Discussion of Draft Regional Regulations is carried out through 4 (four) discussion stages, unless the Deliberation Committee determines otherwise, before discussing stages 2, 3 and 4, a faction meeting is held.

Phase I discussion of the draft regional regulations includes: 1) the Regent's explanation in the plenary meeting regarding the submission of the draft regional regulations; or explanation by the head of the commission/joint commission/special commission regarding the draft regional regulations or changes to regional regulations from the initiative/initiative of the DPRD. The second stage of discussion is: 1) the general views of the factions on the draft regional regulation and the Regent's response to the views of the factions in the plenary meeting, if the draft regional regulation comes from the government/Regent. 2) The Regent's view of the draft regional regulation and the responses from the factions to the Regent's views, if the draft regional regulation comes from the DPRD.

Stage III discussions on draft regional regulations include: 1) discussion at a commission/joint commission meeting or committee meeting, which is held jointly with the Regent or appointed official, 2) if deemed necessary the Deliberation Committee can determine that the third stage of discussions be held at a meeting commission, joint commission or special committee meeting. Phase IV discussions include: 1) decision making at the DPRD Plenary Meeting which is preceded by: a report on the results of phase III discussions, the final opinions of the factions submitted by their members and decision making (approved or rejected) and 2) delivery of the Regent's Address to the decision making. Draft regional regulations can be withdrawn before a joint discussion between the Regent and the DPRD accompanied by clear reasons and obtaining mutual approval for the withdrawal, at a later date the draft cannot be submitted again.

Draft Regional Regulations that have received approval from the DPRD in a plenary meeting, which is marked by a DPRD decision signed by the Chairman or chairman of the plenary meeting, are then submitted no later than 7 (seven) days to the Regent to be adopted as Regional Regulations with a deadline of 30 (thirty) days at the latest. The day after which it is to be promulgated is included in the Regional Gazette and Regional Gazette. In the case of approval of a draft regional regulation regarding the RAPBD to obtain the Governor's approval, an evaluation of higher statutory regulations and public interests is first carried out, only after the Governor approves it can it become a Regional Regulation. Likewise, draft regional regulations regarding taxes, regional levies and spatial planning must obtain permission from the Minister of Finance or other ministers in charge. In research examining efforts to build political support for Regional Heads with the Regional People's Representative Council of Maros Regency in conditions of a divided government system, the data collection process was carried out continuously. In the event that there are aspirations/proposals for development planning, governmental, social, economic or other problems, these aspirations must be immediately accommodated and coordinated with the relevant Services/Agencies with the Commissions in the DPRD according to the context of the problems received. Based on the results of interviews with several faction leaders who said that:

"In general, the Regional Government accommodates development aspirations through first; Development deliberations (MUSBANG) start from the village/sub-district level to the sub-district level and finally at the district level. Second; Direct suggestions/proposals to the Regent and/or Deputy Regent or related Department. Third; through DPRD members directly or during recess. Fourth; programs/activities launched by the Central and/or Provincial Government."

Accommodating aspirations at the Village/Subdistrict level through the Village/Subdistrict development deliberation forum (MUSBANGDES/LUR), this deliberation activity is attended by the Village/subdistrict Community Resilience Institute (LKMD/LPMD), Village/Subdistrict Apparatus and religious/community leaders which is held once a year once (approximately April). The results of the Village/Subdistrict Development Deliberation are brought to the District level development deliberation which is attended by the Village/Subdistrict and representatives of political parties/Council members from the relevant electoral district. The results of the musbangcam resume are brought to the district level to be discussed in the district level priority scale data, so that they become material for the Regional Head's annual work plan.

However, apart from going through the musbang forum, development planning proposals can also be made directly (proposals and/or verbally) to the Regent/Deputy Regent or members of the Maros Regency DPRD. This planning proposal is forwarded to the relevant Department/Institution under the coordination of the Maros Regency Regional Development Planning Agency (BAPPEDA), the Regional Secretary and/or the respective Regional Worker Unit (SKPD).

Concerning proposals from DPRD members either through direct proposals or during recess, the Regent and/or Deputy Regent are very accommodating to include the priority scale list in the current year's programs/activities and/or if they are not accommodated enough, they will be included in changes to the current year's budget.

In addition to strategies for efforts to build political support with the Regional People's Representative Council of Maros Regency through coordination patterns, building networks/networking, collaboration and negotiation and consensus in making regional government policies both in planning regional regulations, regional income and expenditure budget plans as well as forms of accountability reports for their progress. Government in the current year, the regional head's leadership pattern/typology greatly influences the relationship/communication between the regional head and the DPRD.

In his leadership, the Regional Head with the Leaders and Members of the DPRD agreed that in carrying out their authority, main tasks and institutional functions, they must continue to maintain regional conduciveness, the interests of all parties, problem solving efforts rather than making problems worse. Based on the results of an interview with the Chairman of the DPRD, he said that:

"In the policy planning process, the Regent of Maros waited for the planning process from various staff and including opinions from DPRD members, only after obtaining the data did he dare to make a decision, it was seen; In the Regent's letters there are notes, considerations, and coordination with the relevant Services/Agencies coordinated by the Regional Secretary and/or Assistant. (Interview with DPRD Chairman)

There is a change in the paradigm of regional government as a ruler to the paradigm that regional government is a service, so the leadership type of regional heads plays a very important role as the initiator, mover, pioneer and motivator in implementing regional government management, in practicing regional government leadership patterns which tend to be more towards a consultative leadership pattern. and participative, this is evidenced by the fact that every time a decision is made, he always seeks the opinion of the subordinates who handle it directly, he positions

himself as a policy director (steering of policy), in line with Osborne's opinion in Kalloh J, p. 177 15 that there are five regional head strategies so that regional government organizations in accordance with the demands of society in the era of globalization, namely core strategy or core strategy, meaning that regional heads function as policy directors (steering policy) rather than direct implementers or actually as captains.

Coordination

Coordination is regulating an organization, institution, activity so that the rules and actions to be implemented do not contradict each other or be confused but will synergize between organs / structures / functions with each other so that goals can be achieved. Therefore, in order to run a conducive and safe Government, Development and Community Services, communication and coordination measures taken by the Head Regent of Maros Regency with the Maros Regency DPRD such as coordination meetings.

Based on the results of an interview with the Speaker of the DPRD. says that: "The Regional Head Regent in carrying out the duties of autonomy and assistance duties from the Provincial Government and the Central Government, always coordinates with the Regional People's Representative Council of Maros Regency. In carrying out autonomous tasks, especially in making the RAPBD, it is preceded by deliberation on the Development plan (MUSRENBANG) from the Village/Village level with Deliberation on Village/Village Development Plan (MUSRENBANGDES/LUR), Deliberation on District Development Plan (MUSRENBANGCAM) and Deliberation on District Regional Development Plan (MUSRENBANGDA/KAB). In every musrenbang at the sub-district level, political parties (DPRD members in each respective region), as well as in musrenbangda DPRD commissions to participate in the discussion assistance. (Interview of the Speaker of the DPRD). Meanwhile, according to the chairman of commission 1 said that: "Coordination in development planning in Musrenbang and coordination meetings involving executive, legislative, judicial and even community elements shows that the political or democratic process in Maros district runs without experiencing deadlock, so it is in line with the principle of democratic-crazy principle that in formulating policies and overcoming regional problems are discussed with stakeholders with the principle of looking for problem solving or problem-solving efforts.

In line with the opinion of Ralf Dahrendorf, in Ramlan Surbakti, 1999 that conflicts can be resolved through three approaches including conciliation, namely by discussing openly with stakeholders so as to reach an agreement".

Negotiation and Collaboration

Apart from coordination and building networking, negotiation and collaboration also play an important role in organizational functions. Negotiation and collaboration will be able to unite different visions and missions to find common ground for one goal. In negotiations there are two patterns: first, distributive bargaining, this pattern uses a win and lose solution (win-lose) approach, second, integrative bargaining, this pattern uses a win-win solution (win-win) pattern.

Meanwhile, collaboration is a fundamental process of a form of cooperation that gives rise to trust, integrity and breakthroughs through achieving consensus and integration in all aspects of the organization [5].

Negotiation is a bargaining process by negotiating to reach a mutual agreement between one party, group, organization and another, or in other words negotiation is peaceful resolution of disputes through negotiations [6].

In a political process, negotiation is a stage that cannot be missed, because politics is actually a "negotiation" between two or more interests so as to reach an agreement or agreement. Consensus is an agreement or agreement or agreement (opinion, stance, view) together on a particular problem or interest or policy [7].

In the process of running the government system in Maros Regency, the relationship pattern between the Regent as Regional Head and the Maros Regency DPRD; especially regarding the authority, duties and functions of the Regional Head with the DPRD in the areas of Approval of Draft Regional Regulations, Approval of the draft regional income and expenditure budget (RAPBD) and supervisory functions, always trying to carry out a negotiation process in Commission, Committee, Leadership meetings as well as in plenary meeting [8].

In the case of submitting a draft Regional Regulation, the Regent forms a Drafting Team, drafting the Draft Regional Regulation, chaired by the Regional Secretary assisted by the Assistant Regional Secretary/Head of Division and the Department/technical office concerned, to carry out negotiations, while remaining guided by the rules of the game. Applies. Based on the results of an interview with the Regent of Maros, Mr H.A.S Chaidir Syam said that:

The form of negotiation between the Government, which is specifically led by the Regional Secretary and the Maros Regency DPRD, is carried out through lobbying or holding meetings to provide detailed information about differences in perceptions or activities in question. Negotiations or lobbying are carried out to explain the objectives of existing activities, with all the potential and limited resources they have and thank God, differences in perception can be eliminated, so that the political interests of each political party through their respective factions and members can be negotiated with the proposed plan. By the Regional Government, ultimately with one goal for the benefit of the people. (Interview with the Regent of Maros)

So the results of Regional Government policies, whether included in the Approval and Ratification of Regional Regulations or RAPBD in particular, are the result of negotiations/lobbying between the programs planned by the Regent as Regional Government and the political interests carried out by DPRD members from each political party.

The Regent and Deputy Regent of Maros are aware that in order to run the wheels of government, development and social affairs, basic conditions of society are needed, namely the situation and conditions of social life that are conducive, in the sense that if the situation of society, regional institutions such as the DPRD, Regional Government, other Services/Agencies interacting with each other, communicating on each other's main tasks and functions with the aim of the greater interests of the people, not the sectoral interests/egos of each institution or even groups/groups or individuals [9].

So, so that the Regent and Deputy Regent as the executive or government can carry out their mandate for the next 5 years and have the hope of being able to nominate again for the next term of office as Regional Head, according to the Regent the key words are communication, coordination, integration and synchronization to build a

vision and the same goal even though the authorities, duties and obligations are different [5], argues, how can the Government and the DPRD equate the same vision and goals even though the duties, obligations and responsibilities are different, the key words are coordination, integration and synchronization (KIS). So how to build teamwork and convergence in government administration.

Building a Network (Networking)

To be able to unite the vision, the main element is communication. "Networking" is an active process of building and managing productive relationships, both personal and organizational. In a work network, to be able to achieve capabilities, relationships and partnerships, there must be efforts to nurture, cultivate and integrate [10].

The efforts of the Regent and Deputy Regent of Maros to build, maintain and grow networks in political communication in the sense of obtaining political support from the Maros Regency DPRD, namely kinship with political parties.

As is known, the relationship between the Regional Head Regent and the Regional People's Representative Council (DPRD) is like two sides of a coin which are interrelated and cannot stand alone because if there is only one part it will have no meaning but must complement each other. Therefore, in the science of communication, which aims to convey messages so that they have a similar purpose, communication media or networks are an absolute necessity. The more numerous and varied networks you have, the wider and faster the political commodity material (policies) will be, the more planned and supported by all parties [11].

As the results of the 2021 General Election show, there are 16 political parties participating, but only 10 (ten) political parties can obtain seats in the Maros Regency Regional People's Representative Council (DPRD), namely Golkar 7 seats, PAN 6 seats, NASDEM 7 seats, National Awakening Party 4 seats, HANURA 4 seats, Gerindra 3 seats, PKS 2 seats, United Development Party 2 seats, Democrat 1 seat, and PBB 1 seat. The Regent's political communication with each Political Party leader is prioritized so that emotional relationships between political party leaders including leaders of other Political Parties are active and effective, this is because the Regent's vision for the growth and development of political parties is highly upheld, meaning the Regent encourages growth and development. democratic political life, even though he is aware that he was born from the womb of the PAN Party, the vision and political attitude of a Regent belongs to all the people/parties so that he does not only grow the Pan Party, in fact he maintains the same distance from all political parties.

CONCLUSION

This research is directed at analyzing regional heads' strategies for building political support with the DPRD in conditions of divided government in Maros Regency. Based on the description in the previous chapter, it can be concluded from the research that the strategy of regional heads to build political support with the DPRD in conditions of divided government in Maros Regency is carried out in several ways, namely Coordination, Network Building, Negotiation, Collaboration and Consensus, leadership, Prioritizing Community Aspirations Directly. These five strategies are working well and are supported by legislative members in carrying out the vision and mission of the Regent and Deputy Regent of Maros Regency.

Simultaneous elections between DPRD member elections and regional head elections will still be held simultaneously so as not to give rise to Divided Government. Improving the regulations regarding political parties in Indonesia. Strengthening the regulations of the Political Party Law as a legal basis for political parties by detailing the functions of political parties as a means of political communication, political socialization, political recruitment and conflict management.

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